

Designing a Creative Playground with Positive Affects

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Abstract: This study is concerned with designing a creative playground with emotional considerations. At this moment, the available playgrounds in Iran are not equipped with creative games to satisfy children's creativity and learning needs. For this study QFD and Kansei Engineering method was used. These methods are the useful methodologies that help the designers to provide users' emotional needs. Providing positive emotions makes children more creative during play sessions. Twenty five children, thirteen girls and twelve boys between 4 to 12 years old were selected randomly among the children in a playground. They were asked to describe their feelings about their favorite playground. In addition, twenty children were asked to draw paintings about their preferred playground. Regarding children's expressions, two different concepts were generated by two methods. In order to evaluate the children's feelings regarding the two final concepts, another study was carried out with 15 children. The PANA model was used and it was concluded that the QFD concept could have more positive affects on children.

Keywords: *Creativity, Emotions, Playground, Kansei Engineering, QFD.*

1. Introduction

Playing has been known as an area for the expression of creativity and facilitation of creative processes. Play has an important role in developing creativity, because so many of the cognitive and affective processes involved in creativity occur in play [1]. Between 2 to 7 years old, children become imaginative in their play activities and the use of imagination and affect processes become important parts of their playing [2]. Children's play reflects their natural feeling and ability to access, express, and integrate their emotions [3]. So emotion and self-esteem are intertwined within the creative process [4].

Playing and learning are very closely connected. Through play and the repetition of basic physical skills, children complete their abilities and become capable at hard physical tasks. Also it promotes mental development and new ways of thinking and problem solving [5]. One of the strongest benefits of play is the way it enhances social development. Through cooperative games, children gradually learn to take each other's needs into account, and appreciate different values and perspectives. A collaborative game leads not only to positive social values, but also helps children to develop individual skills and creativity [6].

The research on the effect of emotion on information processing in children's mind shows that particular moods trigger unique styles of information processing in learning and creativity. Children's positive emotions make more natural creative thinking during play sessions [7]. For example, emotional calm is a necessary condition for the proper functioning of intellectual power in children or the sense of success creates balanced personalities. Failure, fear, frustration, harsh criticism, sarcasm, punishment, and unhealthy competition will never create the sense of independence and self-control in children. Therefore, all the playing and learning environments should be in the principles of emotional hygiene of children [8].

Children need plenty of opportunities for creative play and thinking. It starts by providing activities that are based on the children's interests and ideas. This means learning how to listen intently to what children say. Apart from drawing and painting, there are many other ways for developing children's creativity, such as photography, music, field trips, working with wire, clay, paper, wood, water or shadows. The possibilities are endless. It's important to provide children lots of time to experiment different materials and pursue their ideas. [9]. Playgrounds are the common space for children to express their emotions and experience collaborative and creative games. It would be useful to learn how to create a hygienic creative playground by asking the children comments and desires [10].

At this moment, the available playgrounds in Iran are not equipped with creative games to satisfy children's creativity and learning needs. In order to find out the Iranian children's desires and design a creative playground, two studies were carried out.

2. First Study

The aim of the first study was to find out the children's desires and design a new creative playground for Iranian children who live in Kish Island. Kish Island is a coral island in Persian Gulf which is located in south of the country. It has a tropical climate with very hot and humid weather. The available playgrounds in Kish are equipped just with the combination of basic playing equipments like swings and slides. They are made of poly propylene in white, blue, purple, yellow, green, orange and red colors (Figure 1).

Figure 1. An available playground in Kish Island

Girls and boys between 4 to 12 years old who live in Kish were selected as a target group. In order to find out the children's desires, twenty five children, thirteen girls and twelve boys form target group were selected randomly in a playground in Kish Island. The children and their parents were interviewed and then twenty of children were asked to paint their desired playground on a paper. After that, they were asked to explain their paintings and emotions. Figure 2 shows some of children's paintings about their

favorite playgrounds. It was tried to get help from children to translate their messages in the painting to the words. For example water that has seen in most of the paintings, which named “water” by children, was translated as a need for a colder environments. Helicopter, clouds, flight, flip-flop, light, dance and some other words obtained as some of children’s wants during painting and chatting.

Figure 2. Some of children’s paintings about their favorite playground

Based on children’s interests two new creative playgrounds were designed by two different methods. Quality Function Deployment and Kansei Engineering are both two popular and useful methods to translate users’ wants to design parameters. To use the best methods, QFD as a quality based one and Kansei Engineering as an emotional tool both were selected to translate children’s desires to design a creative playground.

2.1. Quality Function Deployment Method (QFD)

Quality Function Deployment translates user requirements (voice of customer) into design characteristics. It establishes user value using the voice of customer and transforms that value to design, production, and manufacturing process characteristics [11]. QFD method works with a matrix for mapping the voice of customer to design parameters. This matrix is called House of Quality and has typically seven different steps.

Step 1 - Gathering Users’ requirements: It is also known as "Voice of Customer". They are the users’ wants from the product that needs to be developed. They contain users’ wishes, expectations and requirements for the product. The purpose of this activity is to establish a clear understanding of all of the users’ needs, specifically the subjective performance requirements.

Step 2 - Users importance ratings: Once these users’ requirements are collected, the user’s needs due to the provided numerical ratings to these items would be prioritized in terms of their importance to the user.

Step 3 - Technical specification: The technical specifications are the engineers' understanding in technical terms due to the customers’ want. These data must be quantifiable or measurable.

Step 4 - Relationship matrix: Relationship matrix is used to maintain the relationship between voice of customers and design requirements. It is in the center of House of Quality. A weight of 1-3-9 or 1-3-5 is often used to present the relationships.

Step 5 - Correlation matrix: It is the triangular part of the House of Quality (the roof). The correlation matrix is used to identify, which technical specification items support the others or have conflict with each others. Positive correlations help to identify those technical specifications that are closely related and

avoid duplication of efforts. Negative correlations present conditions that will probably require trade-offs. These ratings are usually quantified between 2 and -2.

Step 6 - Target values: They are specific technical guidance for what have to be achieved. The goals or values have to be quantified in order to be specific and measurable.

Step 7 - Overall importance ratings: This is the final step of House of Quality. The total number of each column places in this part. The results help to identify critical product requirements and assist in the trade-off decision making process [12].

2.1.1. Applying QFD to obtain design parameters of playground

In order to perform QFD process in House of Quality matrix, the children’s wants about their favorite playground were translated to the clear design instructions. In the next step, these Voices of Customers were rated by a professional group from 1 to 100 percent of importance. This group was included ten people who were psychologists, Kindergarten teachers and parents who agreed to participate. As Table 1 shows these rated voice of customers are contributed to eleven key words.

As Table 1 shows being safe, pleasant and educational are the most important attributes of the new playground while being neat has the less importance.

Table 1. The Rated Voice of Customers

Voice of Customer	Importance Rating
Being thin	%60
Being Beautiful	%70
Being Strong	%40
Having shade	%50
Having light	%80
Being Exciting	%100
Being Safe	%100
Being Pleasant	%100
Being Educational	%100
Being Neat	%30
Being Colorful	%60

Following these steps, a market research carried out in order to identify the best playgrounds as competitors. Then the technical specifications of these playgrounds obtained from their catalogues and manuals and applied in QFD process.

These technical specifications were classified to several items, including; Weight, Material type, Overall Dimension, Texture, Form, Color variation, Number of Parts, Size of parts, type of joints, material of joints and material of ground. They were entered as measurable parameters in House of Quality matrix that could be used for design (Figure 3). At the next step, the relationship between voice of customers and technical specifications were identified. A weight of 1-3-5 was used in this study for presenting the relationships. An orange point was used for showing a strong relationship between a customer attribute and an engineering characteristic. While a black point was used for presenting medium relationship and a black triangle for weak relationship.

To find critical product requirements, sum of each column in center part of the House of Quality matrix was calculated. The results as the Engineering Characteristics Importance were shown in the House of Quality matrix in Figure 3. As Figure 3 shows, the material of the parts with 33 scores is the most

important technical specification. Form, texture and the material of the ground are the next important technical issues with 21, 19 and 18 scores. While the overall dimension of playground, the number of joints and the forms and textures variation have less scores. It shows that these technical specifications are not very important issues in designing a new playground.

After obtaining the critical engineering characteristics, the target value for each technical detail was investigated from the competitors' specifications and standards. Each target value was chosen from the best engineering characteristic. These are the values which used as targets in finding sub-solutions and generating alternatives phase in design process. The result of target value is presented in Figure 4. Regarding the target values which obtained from QFD matrix, several concepts were generated. Due to the children's interests and voice of customers, one of these concepts was selected as the final concept.

Figure 3. The QFD Matrix

EC importance	14	17	33	6	19	21	8	4	11	10	12	9	5	13	15	18
units	N							m				m				
targets	2-45	4 Kinds of material	Stainless steel-Densified polyethylene foam-Polypropylene-Styrene-Butadiene	4 Kinds of texture	Soft and Smooth curve	14 Kinds of form	Height: 2- Radius: 1 Meters	Colorful	7 Colors- Red, Orange, Green, Blue, Yellow, Black, Silver	36 Parts	Height: 2- Length: 0.9 meters	9 Joints	Polypropylene- Stainless steel	Groove and tongue	Styrene Butadiene Rubber	

Figure 4. The Target Values of Technical Specification

The final concept is a playground with both collaborative and individual games. It has approximately 200 centimeter height and 200 centimeter diameter. This playground includes two different parts that are related to each other. Puzzle game and painting field are the main parts of the playground.

The Puzzle game is a 3D puzzle that consists of 9 pieces. In the complete form, these pieces would make a 3D Helicopter. Each piece of the helicopter is made of colored Densified Poly Ethylene Foam. There is a stainless steel bar in the center of the puzzle. It has 200 centimeter height and 5 centimeter diameter. All the pieces are hung from poly propylene blades which keep them in 70 centimeters height. All pieces would be attached by Groove and Tongue joints to each other and to a platform. The platform is made of Poly Propylene and all of the pieces of the helicopter would be attached on it. If children attach the pieces of puzzle correctly, the helicopter will be complete and its blades start to rotate. After that children can complete the painting that is under the helicopter. The painting field is a sheet of S.B.Rubber with 40 mm thickness. It is soft and children could be able to stretch themselves out on it and enjoy from their painting. The different steps of the playground are shown in Figure5.

Figure 5. (left to right) Step1-Children complete the puzzle
Step 2-Blades start to rotate and children begin to paint on the painting field

2.2. Kansei Engineering Method (KE)

One of the design methods, which is able to capture the user's feelings and translate them into concrete design is Kansei Engineering. According to a general model on Kansei Engineering procedure, the basic idea is to focus on the product from two different perspectives. These perspectives are the semantic description space and the description of product properties space. Subsequently these spaces are merged in with each other in synthesis phase. This phase indicates which of the product properties evokes which semantic impact.

From this model an experiment design was derived, which interconnected the relations between users' Kansei and design elements. This procedure basically contains four different steps.

Step 1 – Collecting Kansei Words

The first step is to assess the customer's perception about the specific product. Therefore the customer feelings and desires have to be identified and expressed with Kansei words.

Step 2 - Structuring Kansei words

In second step, those Kansei words would be arranged on a Semantic Differential Scale to be able to measure the customer's perception.

Step 3 - product Properties

The product of concern has to be defined in the next step and its design elements have to be classified to items and categories.

Step 4 – Synthesis

Finally, these data would be analyzed with Category Classification to determine the contribution of each design element on the user perception [13].

2.2.1. Applying Kansei Engineering to obtain design parameters of playground

For applying Kansei engineering method to design a new creative playground, words from different resources about playgrounds, collaborative games, creativity and other related titles were investigated and collected. Also the words which obtained from interview and children’s painting were considered too as Kansei words.

Sixty seven adjectives were obtained as Kansei words. For structuring the Kansei words, these collected adjectives were analyzed and categorized. Then, from each category a word or a group of words were chosen as a representative. So the number of the words reduced to 30. These words were investigated again and finally 16 words were selected as higher-level kansei words. Table2 shows these chosen higher-level Kansei words.

In next step according to the product domain, playground properties and details identified. Furthermore, some design elements like color variations, forms and textures were investigated by Conjoint Trend Analysis. In order to perform CTA method, a Trend Board was prepared. The images of Iranian children’s favorite toys, cartoons, games, meals, animated characters, books, and illustrations and so on in Kish Island were collected and formed as a board that is shown in Figure 6.

Table 2. The chosen Higher-Level Kansei Words

Higher-Level Kansei Words	
Short	Attractive
Soft	Educational
Cool	Funny
Hard	Safe
Clean	Flip-flop
Soppy	Fluid
Collaborative	Physical
Dynamic	Simple

The forms, textures and colors of images in Trend board were determined and analyzed. The most repetitive elements were defined as the design palette and presented as the CTA results. These results as a design data base are presented Figure 7. As Figure 7 shows curved lines and circles in forms, soft, glossy and stripy in texture and red, blue, green, orange, white and black in color were identified as design elements.

Figure 6. The Trend Board of children

Figure 7. The CTA results

Regarding the Kansei words, playground specifications and design elements, many concepts were generated. Due to the children's interests and desires, one of these concepts was selected as the best and final concept. The final concept consists of 6 routs of pipe. All these pipes are connected to the final target, which is a plastic whale. These routs are curvy with some complications which have to be solved. This playground could be installed in a ground with approximate 5 meter length and 5 meter width with flexibility to be increased or decreased in different areas.

The Game that designed for this playground is a collaborative game that six children can play with it at the same time. It is made of polypropylene pipes with 300 centimeters length, 30cm diameter and 2cm thickness. These pipes are transparent with 0.4 densities to be soft, flexible and safe for children (Isotactic polymers). There is some colorful water flowing in pipes. The colors are blue, green, yellow, orange, red and natural water. There is a big water bed with 200cm diameter. In order to start the game, children need to jump on it to flow the water in the pipes. There are also eight small colored water beds, two for each valve. The diameter of each water bed is 40cm. The pipes are connected to each other. Four of these connections are gate-valves with colored lights. Each valve has two lights in different colors. One of the lights has the same color as the water flow, which is the right choice of the game. Other one has different color, which is the wrong choice. The light for the right choice starts to flash when water reach at the related gate. In order to open the gate, children should jump on the bed which has the same color as the light. That means the water would flow in other pipes and can reach to the destination. The target is the transparent polypropylene whale which must be filled with water. The whale has 200cm length, 80cm width and 100cm height. Since the whale is filled with water, 50cc water would splash from the whale head. The whale would empty gradually and the game would be finished. The different steps of the playground are shown in Figure 8. If children jump on the wrong bed 50cc of cold natural water would splash from holes on the ground. This makes children wet and the gate of the valve wouldn't open. That means the game is over.

Figure 8. (left to right) Step 1- children must jump on big water bed Step 2- children follow the colorful water in pipes Step 3- the final target is to fill the plastic whale

The final concept formed due to children’s Kansei words. Therefore, the means of each Kansei word can be seen in the concept. The relation between different parts of the concept and Kansei words is presented in table 3. As table 3 shows each playground specification was designed due to the related kansei word. For example waterbed was designed in playground for jumping, which is related to Flip-Flop and Dynamic kansei words.

Table 3. The relationship between children’s Kansei words and new playground specifications

Higher-Level Kansei Words	Playground Specifications
Short	Pipe with 30cm diameter
Soft, Safe, Unbreakable	Isotactic polymer pipe with 0.4 density
Fluid	Flowing water in transparent pipes
Attractive	Colorful flowing waters in transparent pipes
Flip-Flop, Dynamic	Water beds
Educational	Color notification and water navigation
Physical	Jumping on water beds
Soppy, Cool, Funny	Splashing water

3. Second Study

The aim of the second study was to select the best playground among the two concepts which obtained by QFD and KE methods. To perform this study, two concepts were evaluated by children emotional responses.

1.3. Methods

In order to evaluate these two concepts regarding children’s feelings and emotions, Positive Affect and Negative Affect model (PANA) was used. PANA is one of the Self-Rated Affect models that emerged reliably as the main dimensions of emotional experiences. This model consists of two scales for PA and NA respectively. These two scales consist of ten words and phrases that describe different feelings and emotions in positive and negative areas [14].

Fifteen children from one of kindergarten in Kish Island were selected randomly. They were between 5 to 7 years age and various in genders. This kindergarten was located nearby one of those playgrounds and children were brought to play in it commonly. A showroom was prepared and the two concepts were presented in isometric perspectives on A3 papers. The two playground concepts have been shown step by step on papers. It was tried to get help from the kindergarten preceptors to explain the playgrounds by pictures, stories and activities to children. Then children were asked to explain their feelings as words regarding the each concept. For each concept, all the words were investigated and collected. Each word was analyzed and classified regarding the Positive Affect and Negative Affect criteria. The criteria of PANA model are shown in Figure 9.

Positive affect (PA)	Attentive, Interested, Alert, Excited, Enthusiastic, Inspired, Proud, Determined, Strong, Active
Negative affect (NA)	Distressed, Upset, Hostile, Irritable, Scared, Afraid, Ashamed, Guilty, Nervous, Jittery

Figure9. Positive Affect and Negative Affect Model

As Figure 9 shows the affects in Positive category as the criteria are good moods and feelings like excited, inspired and active. While the criteria of Negative affect category are bad feelings such as upset,

scared and nervous. In final step, all of the children’s affects regarding the two concepts were classified and compared.

2.3. Results

The results of the PANA model classification are summarized in Table 4. As Table 4 shows from the 15 words regarding the playground that designed with QFD method, 12 words are classified as Positive Affect and 3 words are in Negative category. About the Playground which designed with KE method, 11 words are in Positive and 4 of them classified as Negative Affect. Table 4 also shows that Interested and Excited as Positive Affects are repeated more than any other affect among children in KE concept. In the other side, Inspired and Excited from Positive and Nervous from Negative categories are the most repetitive affect for the QFD concept.

Table 4. The PANA model classification of children’s emotional words regarding two playgrounds

Playground Designed With Kansei Engineering Method				Playground Designed With QFD Method			
words	Positive Affect	words	Negative Affect	words	Positive Affect	words	Negative Affect
fresh	Interested			colorful	Inspired		
solving	Determined			solved	Proud		
curious	Alert			having a helicopter	Enthusiastic		
		big whale	Scared			hard to solve	Irritable
		lost	Afraid			cannot solve it	Nervous
wining	Strong			solving	Determined		
clapping hands	Excited			having a helicopter	Excited		
sharing with others	Active			curious	Alert		
		loosing	Nervous	making it immediately	Active		
cool	Interested			solving	Strong		
jumping	Excited			beautiful	Interested		
wining	Proud			painting	Inspired		
		defeat	Hostile	making puzzle	Attentive		
solving	Attentive					hard to solve	Nervous
colorful	Inspired			having a helicopter	Excited		
11		4		12		3	

3.3. Discussion

According to the first study, the collections of children’s words indicate that children like collaborative educational games in their playground. They also required safe, soft, beautiful, colorful and exciting equipments in playgrounds. These words were translated as Voice of Customer to safe, pleasant and exciting playground. They required beautiful environment which is equipped with light for night and shade for days. In QFD matrix these attributes were translated to the technical specification of a new playground. A new playground that has curved forms, soft and smooth textures with seven different colors. By employing the QFD results, several concepts were generated and the best of them were selected as the final concept. Final concept was a 3D model of a helicopter in 9 pieces puzzle with a rubber painting field. In this concept children would be able to play individually and collaboratively. They could just paint or make a puzzle and paint. They learn to touch and experience things and solve the

puzzle problem. In the end they would make a complete thing that starts to work. Children in new playground learn collaboration with other children to have fun and pleasant time.

The Kansei words show that the children love wet, sappy and cool conditions for playing. They enjoy dynamic, physical and flip-flop games. The playground also requires being equipped with funny and simple games, which are attractive enough to play. According to CTA study in Iranian kids' trends, the curved lines, soft and noisy texture and a collection of red, orange, yellow, blue, green, black and white colors are the elements, which should be used as design data base. The final playground is large and many children could play in it at the same time. The color notification process to navigate the flowing water in different pipes helps children to learn and recognize different colors and cooperation to get the target.

The second study shows that kids have more positive affect for the playground that designed with QFD method. They were so inspired with colorful puzzle and painting on rubber field. They were also excited about the helicopter which worked. However Table 4 shows that they were also nervous about the difficulty of the puzzle for solving it. Using colorful, soft and light puzzle which required physical and mental activities to solve Using helps to provide satisfaction for children. At the end by the complete helicopter which starts to rotate children would experience the successful and obtain satisfaction feeling.

As table 4 shows the concept that designed with Kansei Engineering method had Positive Affects on children too. They were interested in fresh and cool water that splashed from the whale and holes in the game and excited about colorful fluid water in transparent pipes and jumping on water beds. However the number of positive affects on children was less that the QFD concept.

4.3. Conclusion

Playing is the most serious activity for children. Designing a suitable playground and providing appropriate emotional situations during playing have a very important role in developing children's creativity. In this study QFD and Kansei Engineering method as two popular methods for capturing and translating users' interests were used to design a creative playground in Kish Island. Then the selected concepts from each method were evaluated by PANA model to identify the kids' feelings about it. The results of the study show that children loved the new playground which designed by QFD method. It seems this concept had more positive affects on children because of its helicopter and painting equipments. Employing different materials and textures, curved lines and colorful pieces makes children excited. Furthermore, using rotating blades which worked as a fan top of children's heads during painting fascinates children.

This study also showed that QFD with the ability of translating users' needs and desire to Engineering characteristics could be a very useful applied methodology. It captured the children's feelings and desires to design a playground, which excites them to play and experience happy moments.

To find more precise results, this study would be repeated with prototypes of these two concepts as further work.

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